

THE CURRENT SUCCESS OF DIGITAL PR

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ABSTRACT

The relevance of the study is determined by the development of Internet technologies that have significantly changed world information landscape, dynamics and structure of mass and interpersonal communications. Analysis of different formats of PR messages, approaches to building relationships with target audiences and organizations' reputation on the Internet confirmed that perception of information by a mass audience, images of public opinion leaders, as well as the level of trust in them are significantly affected by the wide spread of the Internet, availability of digital technologies, popularity of electronic forms of communication and growth of social media.

Introduction

A new stage in the development of the pr industry is associated mainly with the intrusion of digital technologies into the media landscape and communication processes at all levels.

According to global communications report 2016, the development of the pr industry is primarily connected with learning and effective application of new technologies by pr specialists [http://www.holmesreport.com/ranking-and-data/global-communications-report].it is noted that among professionals in the field of

communications, among the most popular are those who have the skills of social media expertise (experience in social media), as well as multimedia content development (creation of multimedia content). Due to global nature of the given tendency, we would like to emphasize that the pr industry of uzbekistan is developing in the same direction.

Materials and methods

Rapid development of internet technologies had a significant impact on the state of the modern pr industry and determined further development of the industry (figure 1).

Figure 1: Transformation of PR industry in the context of digital technologies development

With the development of internet technologies, social media in particular, companies and organizations are able to directly build communications with target audiences. Internet users from passive recipients of information are transformed into active creators and distributors of it, which is reflected in the public relations industry as well. Audiences are becoming interested in taking direct part in pr projects.

Social networks today are not just means of interpersonal communication, but also serious tools of influence. Oversaturation of the market with information significantly influenced on the work of the pr-specialists: it is more difficult for companies and brands to compete for the attention of the audience.

Pr-professionals are eager to cooperate with speakers, whom their target audience trusts, and whose advice is followed. The study allowed coming to the conclusion that the development of internet technologies, social networks in particular,

had an impact on the current understanding of the opinion leader.

Results and discussion

In modern discussions about the future transformations of information and communication sphere, the phenomenon of digitalization has different interpretations. The british "dictionary of media and communication studies" interprets the notion of digitalization as follows: "the computer works digitally: information is broken down into a code of zeros and ones (bits). Today, all forms of electronic communication are converging through digital formats, and computer-mediated communication now applies to newspapers, telephone systems, broadcasting, film production as well as the internet" (watson and hill 2012).

With the advent of the internet in our life, more precisely, with the active development of the concept of web 2.0, the main feature of which is the possibility of active participation of users in filling the online space with information, there have been serious changes in the sphere of pr (figure 2).

Communication with target audiences

Figure 2: Communication with target audiences

It is the possibility to make direct contact with target community groups significantly changed the approach to implementing PR-objectives, on the one hand, providing communication professionals with amazing opportunities for interaction with the audience, and on the other hand, creating new complexities and risks.

Blogs, social networks, wiki-projects “took away” mass media’s palm of victory in the issues of creating content and the degree of influence on society, and opened new

horizons for PR-specialists. Today, communication professionals are learning new forms of information delivery in the context of the digital environment: SMM, storytelling, infographic, blogging, application development, gamification and others. Today, public relations specialists can monitor the entire communication process.

Technological innovations also influenced both on the interaction of PR managers and the mass media (Figure 3).

Modern media relations

Figure 3: Modern media relations

We will pay attention to interactive Internet platforms between media workers and PR specialists.

Conclusion

Modern society enters a new phase of information development in the situation of the intensive influence of information on the progress of mankind, the speed of receiving, the volume and quality of which, become a factor of the sustainable and

effective functioning of economic and social systems. During this time period, we can see obvious interest in the topic. In the academic community, the problem becomes topical and debated. The terms “digitalization”, digital PR in recent years have become quite often used in both professional-theoretical and popular sources as well.

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